

Benchmark a Firewall Rulebase

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1. Preface

This paper was written in 2013 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20130620> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

Firewall systems are the oldest elements in the network security. With ongoing use they were surrounded by many additional security systems but remain a central element of the company security.

As explained by Marc Ruef in *Firewall Rule Review – Ansatz und Möglichkeiten* [1], scip AG performs *firewall rulebase reviews* [2] using self engineered models and tools; please refer to this lab for details.

In this lab, we will briefly discuss the output of our analysis.

3. Data Set

The numbers are calculated using a subset of 30 analyzed rulebases, selected by company type and size, rulebase size and enforcement point (EP) positions (border firewalls with internet exposition, second level or internal firewall):

Figure: Firewall Rulebase Data Distribution

4. Measuring the Rulebase

Our tool searches for vulnerabilities in each rule; each vulnerability has some numerical values associated, some of them can be compared across different rulebases and are useful as indicators.

The *vulnerability-weight* (vw) tries to measure the severity of the identified vulnerability. For each finding, the value is added to the *global rule-weight* (rw). The resulting rw gives a numerical indication of how problematic the rule is.

5. Vulnerability Heatmap

The simplest numerical indicator for each rule is the rw. The whole rulebase can be displayed as a *heatmap*, with the rw as *temperature* indicator as shown in the following table:

Rule	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
0	0	0	11	224	224	0	0	11	0	224	101	0	0	0	101	101	0	454	0	0
20	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	101
40	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	0	0	11	0	0	0	0	0	0
60	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
80	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	101	11	0	0	11	11	101	101	11	0	101	0
100	101	1256	11	224	0	0	0	11	11	0	101	101	0	11	11	11	11	11	0	0
120	0	0	0	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0
140	0	0	0	0	0	0	44	44	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	101
160	101	101	101	224	0	11	0	0	0	11	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	11	224
180	0	0	224	0	0	0	101	0	11	0	11	11	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
200	0	0	0	224	101	101	101	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	101	11	0	0
220	0	0	11	11	101	101	11	11	224	224	0	0	0	0	0	11	11	224	0	0
240	0	0	224	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	0	11	0	11	0	0
260	0	0	0	101	101	101	101	0	11	11	0	11	11	101	0	0	0	11	0	0
280	0	0	101	101	11	11	101	101	0	101	0	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	0
300	0	0	101	101	101	101	101	101	0	224	224	101	101	0	11	0	0	0	0	11
320	0	11	0	0	224	101	101	0	101	0	0	0	44	11	11	101	101	11	0	11
340	0	0	0	0	101	101	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	0	0	11	0	101
360	101	0	101	101	101	101	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
380	0	11	11	0	0	0	101	101	0	11	44	0	224	0	11	11	224	224	1256	0
400	0	0	0	404	224	11	0	839	11	0	0	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	11
420	0	0	11	101	101	101	101	0	101	101	101	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
440	0	0	11	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	224	224	224	224	224	454	224	224	224
460	11	0	0	101	101	0	101	404	101	0	0	0	224	224	11	11	0	224	224	0
480	44	11	0	0	224	101	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	224	0	224	0	101	101
500	0	11	101	101	0	0	101	101	0	0	224	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
520	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0
540	404	0	11	0	0	0	11	11	101	101	0	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	0
560	0	0	0	0	101	101	11	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	101	0	101	101	101
580	0	224	224	11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	101	224	224	11	101
600	101	101	101	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	101	0	101	101	0	0
620	0	0	0	101	0	0	0	0	0	101	0	0	0	0	224	0	101	101	101	11
640	0	11	0	0	224	224	0	0	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	101	101	0	11	0
660	0	0	0	0	101	0	11	0	0	0	101	101	0	0	0	0	101	101	0	11
680	0	369	369	11	11	0	0	0	369	369	11	0	101	101	839	839	0	0	0	0

Figure: Firewall Rule Heatmap

The heatmap may show problematic rule-clusters, as example created for a specific application implementation. Example of rule-cluster candidate for closer look are:

- 453-460
- 124-131
- 363-368

Heatmaps are very rulebase specific, but we can use the data to extract some indicators:

- max(rw)
- avg(rw)
- sum(rw)

The first two are comparable across different rulebases, useful to benchmark the rulebase versus sector or averages rulebases. The last one make sense only for the same rulebase and can be used to measure if the rulebase evolves in the right or wrong direction.

6. Key Areas

During the review, our tools perform hundreds of checks on rulebase core elements (rules, objects, services). We have categorized these checks in *Areas* described as:

Area	Description
Lazy-tracking	This check group basically tries to find out if the rule is <i>well tracked</i> . Administrators tend to aggregate protocols – especially administrative protocols – in few rules, then disable tracking for a rule because an <i>snmp</i> fills the log but at the same time the rule allows also <i>ssh</i> .
Over-Traffic	Sometime we find <i>bi-directional rules</i> , most of which are not really needed: normally, just the traffic in one direction must be explicitly allowed. This check group recursively compares each rule versus all remaining and points out all suspected full or partials rule-pairs.
Readability	Not very frequent, but sometime we encounter a <i>big list of objects</i> defined as source, destination or services. Sometime, the complete rule cannot be displayed on the monitor forcing the user to scroll up and down to search a specific objects. After a while, the rule becomes a blackbox.
Lazy-objecting	Very frequent, objects are <i>not strictly defined</i> ; even if only a single host needs access, the whole network is configured in the rule. This check group points to big objects looking at the number of IPs or ports involved.
Temp/Test	Also frequent, created for quick problem resolution or for <i>temporary access</i> , the objects remain in place sometimes submerged in a group.
Mix	A <i>mix</i> of temporary/test objects with sensitive objects – like administrative objects – is present in some rulebases and is very difficult to find. This check group looks in rule comments, object comments, known services to point out all suspicious combinations for a closer look.

Quality	Basically, we try to measure the <i>quality of the management processes</i> used to manage the rulebases, looking at content of the comments, rulenames etc. Very oft, we encounter redundat or void comments or no reference to a management document, making the rule obscure. See <i>Structuring the Rule Name in Checkpoint Firewall</i> [3]
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Key Area Indicators look a little bit deeper into the rulebase and are used to identify problem areas for an accurate control:

Key Area	Average	Assurance	Finance	Provider
Lazy-tracking	2.50%	1.70%	1.86%	0.97%
Over-traffic	3.18%	1.93%	1.55%	3.87%
Readability	0.09%	0.17%	0.00%	0.00%
Lazy-objecting	2.48%	2.24%	2.13%	1.06%
Temp/Test	1.17%	0.40%	0.54%	1.17%
Mix	0.28%	0.23%	0.34%	0.85%
Quality	6.90%	4.25%	5.46%	3.67%

Figure: Firewall Rulebase Key Area Indicators

Representing the same data as the chart, we can quickly check if the rulebase is performing better or worse in its class.

Figure: Firewall Rulebase Key Area Comparison

7. Key Values

For each Area, many controls are performed on each object. We calculate some *Key Values Indicators* that can be benchmarked across all analyzed rulebases and give us hints on the possible directions for an improvement:

Key Value	Key Area	Max	Average	Assurance	Finance	Provider
Found lazy-tracking rules. There is a mix between 'mustlog' and 'nonlog' protocols.	Lazy-tracking - [2]	19.11%	2.88%	2.04%	2.12%	0.88%
Found lazy-tracking rules. There are only 'mustlog' protocols.	Lazy-tracking - [3]	9.55%	1.46%	1.02%	1.15%	0.49%
Found lazy-tracking rules. There is a mix between 'mustlog', 'nonlog' and 'log' protocols.	Lazy-tracking - [4]	9.55%	1.50%	1.02%	1.06%	0.64%
Found lazy-tracking rules. There are only 'log' protocols.	Lazy-tracking - [5]	9.55%	1.61%	1.02%	1.50%	1.34%
Found lazy-tracking rules. There is a mix of 'nonlog' and 'log' protocols.	Lazy-tracking - [6]	26.66%	4.42%	3.10%	3.22%	1.52%
Found lazy-tracking rules. There is a mix of 'mustlog' and 'log' protocols.	Lazy-tracking - [7]	19.11%	2.91%	2.04%	2.12%	0.94%
Found partial bi-directional rule.	Over-traffic - [9]	0.79%	0.31%	0.35%	0.12%	0.03%
Found partial bi-directional rule pair.	Over-traffic - [12]	4.72%	1.64%	1.58%	0.39%	0.68%
Found full bi-directional rule.	Over-traffic - [15]	10.24%	4.12%	3.51%	4.67%	2.21%
Found full bi-directional rule pair.	Over-traffic - [16]	20.37%	6.63%	2.29%	1.01%	11.57%
Found rule with high number of objects in [Source].	Readability - [25]	0.79%	0.13%	0.17%	0.00%	0.00%
Found rule with high number of objects in [Destination].	Readability - [36]	0.79%	0.10%	0.17%	0.00%	0.00%
Found rule with high number of objects in [Service].	Readability - [37]	0.37%	0.03%	0.19%	0.00%	0.00%
Found rule with [Source] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [17]	9.62%	3.33%	1.39%	3.16%	0.97%
Found rule with [Destination] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [18]	12.80%	5.02%	0.37%	4.64%	1.40%
Found rule with [Source] and [Destination] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [19]	3.15%	0.57%	0.19%	0.12%	0.00%
Found rule with [Service] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [20]	10.46%	7.93%	13.53%	5.37%	4.60%
Found rule with [Source] and [Service] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [21]	0.48%	0.06%	0.09%	0.48%	0.09%
Found rule with [Destination] and [Service] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [22]	1.11%	0.25%	0.00%	1.15%	0.35%
Found rule with [Source], [Destination] and [Service] that contains 'Any'.	Lazy-objecting - [23]	0.79%	0.18%	0.09%	0.00%	0.03%
Found rule with [Comment] that indicates Temporary/Text rule.	Temp/Text - [24]	8.25%	2.60%	0.50%	3.21%	2.90%
Found rule with [Source] that contains object(s) identified as Temporary/Text object(s).	Temp/Text - [25]	2.91%	1.13%	0.28%	0.62%	1.05%
Found rule with [Destination] that contains object(s) identified as Temporary/Text object(s).	Temp/Text - [26]	4.31%	0.69%	0.83%	0.00%	0.72%
Found rule with [Service] that contains object(s) identified as Temporary/Text object(s).	Temp/Text - [27]	1.59%	0.27%	0.00%	0.30%	0.00%
Found mix of administrative and temporary objects.	Mix - [42]	0.73%	0.13%	0.00%	0.00%	1.16%
Found mix of 'Any' and temporary objects.	Mix - [43]	1.57%	0.29%	0.41%	0.50%	0.97%
Found mix of administrative objects and unsafe protocols.	Mix - [44]	1.59%	0.42%	0.24%	0.48%	0.44%
Found rule allowing protocol(s) considered unsafe.	Quality - [29]	11.85%	6.53%	9.78%	3.58%	6.25%
Found rule with not well formatted [comment].	Quality - [28]	36.13%	17.18%	2.94%	16.50%	8.10%
Found disabled rule.	Quality - [8]	14.65%	3.81%	4.17%	1.63%	0.33%
Found hidden rule.	Quality - [45]	0.64%	0.07%	0.09%	0.07%	0.00%

Figure: "height="

As a chart, we can quickly check which part of the rulebase is performing better or worse.

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8. Challenges

Maintain the same vulnerabilities classification over the years is the biggest challenge for this class of tools.

If the number of checks or the check itself is changed, the result may become not comparable and we would lose all the historical series (sometime was necessary to align old results with the new tools to make values consistent).

During the last decade of constant revisions, we gained a set of consistent checks. While the checking mechanism remains basically the same, the parameters are constantly

updated with each revision: if during an analysis we encounter a new parameter that affects a control, it is coded so that it can be reused in subsequent versions (the most common example is new – sometimes fancy – comments to mark a rule as temporary).

This method reduces the need to (re-)normalize the data while the tool evolves.

9. Summary

Measuring objects with complex interdependencies is always a kind of alchemy and always produces a grainy representation of reality.

Once the process is tuned to (assuming the distortion remains constant), a review of an even larger base of rules becomes not only possible but efficient and through the use of metrics it is possible to steer the improvements and measure them.

Thanks to the experience gained through years of revisions, after countless tests and improvements, we reached a set of checks that help us to measure and improve the quality and security of a rulebase.

10. References

- Gagliardi, Rocco. *Structuring the Rule Name in Checkpoint Firewall* [4]
- Ruef, Marc. *Firewall Rule Parsing am Beispiel von SonicWALL* [5]
- Ruef, Marc. *Firewall Rule Review – Ansatz und Möglichkeiten* [6]

11. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120607>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?dienstleistungen.firewallrulereview>
- [3] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120510>
- [4] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120510>
- [5] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20110113>
- [6] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20120607>